

GUT MICROBIOTA AND HUMAN HEALTH

Gulchekhra Otabek qizi Otabekova
Ozodjon Ilkhomovich Ergashov

Student of the Tashkent International Kimyo University, Scientific Secretary of the Tashkent Scientific Research Institute of Vaccines and Serums,
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Relevance. In recent years, scientific research has shown that the intestinal microflora (beneficial microorganisms in the intestine) is associated with the immune system, mental health, metabolic disorders (e.g., obesity, diabetes), cardiovascular diseases, and even brain function [1, 2]. Currently, numerous clinical studies conducted around the world prove a close relationship between specific types of microbes and human health, which causes eubiosis, and various diseases. That is why the connection between the intestinal microflora and human health is considered very relevant today [3,4].

The purpose of the study. The study of the effect of the composition and diversity of the intestinal microbiota on human health.

Research materials and methods. The study was conducted at the clinic of the Tashkent International University of Chemistry. The methods of retrograde analysis, bacteriological analysis, metagenomic, metabolomic, bioinformatic analysis, and metotranscriptomy were studied for the study. These analysis methods focus on the 16S ribosomal RNA gene, which is highly conserved among bacteria and allows species identification and phylogenetic analysis. Also, analyzing the composition of DNA, analyzing the composition and functions of the intestinal microbiota, sequencing RNA, determine the functional capabilities of microorganisms, which genes are actively expressed.

Results and analyses. These studies explore the relationship between the composition of the gut microbiota and human health on a population basis to provide insight into how various diseases characteristic of microbiota disorders develop. Studies have shown a close relationship between the composition of the intestinal microbiota and the functioning of the immune system, as well as the role of the normal microbiota in preventing various infectious and somatic diseases. Different levels of intestinal microbiota disorders (dysbiosis) also have a strong effect on metabolism, leading to several chronic diseases, including type 2 diabetes, hepatosis, various types of allergies, and even neurological disorders such as depression. In a number of experiments, it has been found that the preventive use of probiotics and prebiotics has a positive effect on the composition of the intestinal microbiota and, thus, improves overall health.

According to recent studies, it is confirmed that the gut microbiota can influence mental and emotional health through neurochemical signaling.

Conclusion. The gut microbiota is an integral part of human health. Its composition and functional state affect the functioning of the whole organism. An imbalance of the microbiota can be a major factor in the development of various diseases. Therefore, maintaining the normal state of the intestinal microbiota is essential for the health of the entire body.

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